

Generation of Elliptically and Circularly Polarized Digital Holograms

David Ekuwom Kaile

National institute for optics and Lasers, Multimedia University, Kenya

Duke Nyangau Onsure

Biological and Physical Sciences Department, Karatina University, Kenya

Stephen Maina Njoroge ✉

Biological and Physical Sciences Department, Karatina University, Kenya

Geoffrey Kihara Rurimo

National institute for optics and Lasers, Multimedia University, Kenya

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Abstract

Holography is a powerful imaging technique that enables the recording and reconstruction of three-dimensional images, with applications spanning imaging systems and optical computing. Traditionally, holographic recording has relied on non-polarized, isotropic materials whose optical properties remain constant in all directions imposing limitations on hologram quality and diversity. Previous studies on linearly polarized holograms revealed potential but faced challenges such as reduced resolution, obscured features, and low-amplitude signal capture. While some work has explored the role of polarization angle on linear hologram resolution, other polarization states remain underexplored. This study addresses this gap by generating elliptically and circularly polarized digital holograms, recorded with a charge-coupled device at an optimal object-to-sensor distance of 15 cm. Numerical reconstruction and noise reduction techniques were applied, resulting in high-resolution holograms that capture a richer set of light wave characteristics, including intensity, phase, and polarization state. Circularly polarized holograms exhibited superior resolution and clarity, with distinct surface texture, depth, and shape features, attributable to enhanced light-object interaction and minimized noise. Elliptically polarized holograms also demonstrated improved phase encoding and depth information relative to linear holograms, though with slightly reduced resolution due to partial beam obstruction and phase gradients. These findings highlight the critical role of polarization control in advancing holographic imaging, broadening its applicability in diverse scientific and technological fields.

Keywords: *hologram, phase, polarization, polarization angle.*

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Introduction

Diffraction efficiency is a critical metric in evaluating the resolution and overall quality of holograms. Despite advances in holographic

imaging, many potential applications remain underexplored due to limitations such as material constraints and the inability to fully retrieve the light wave characteristics encoded within holograms (Njoroge & Kinyua, 2023;

Pawar *et al.*, 2010; Ackermann *et al.*, 2023; Arbabi *et al.*, 2015; Dhar *et al.*, 2008; Jiang *et al.*, 2014; Li *et al.*, 2021; Olivares-Pérez *et al.*, 2015).

To address these limitations and expand the applicability of holography, recent research has focused on the development of linearly polarized holograms, which allow for better analysis of wavefront parameters such as intensity distribution, phase, and amplitude. Unlike conventional holographic techniques which often ignore the polarization state of light polarization holography has emerged as a superior alternative. This is primarily due to its ability to encode additional information, including the polarization state, which plays a pivotal role in advanced optical applications such as data storage, encryption, and sensing (Jianhua *et al.*, 2017; Kuroda *et al.*, 2011; Ruiz *et al.*, 2013; Su *et al.*, 2019; Wei *et al.*, 2019; Ominde *et al.*, 2013).

The concept of polarization holography was first introduced in 1948 with the proposal of a phase hologram recording method based on the interference of orthogonally polarized light beams on a photo-anisotropic medium. This theoretical framework was later verified experimentally and enabled the encoding and reconstruction of polarized light information. Since then, polarization holography has found application in areas such as diffractive optics, flat optics, vortex beam generation, and the manipulation of complex light fields (Ozols *et al.*, 2011; Zhai *et al.*, 2020; Barada *et al.*, 2012; Cardano *et al.*, 2012; Tiwari *et al.*, 2020; Zhao *et al.*, 2021).

Initially, the recording and reconstruction processes in polarization holography were modeled using Jones matrix formalism. However, this model assumed that the two interfering beams were nearly parallel, limiting the analysis to paraxial conditions. These constraints were later addressed by the introduction of tensor-based polarization holography models, which allow for a more generalized treatment of the recording geometry.

Linearly polarized holography has been shown to improve resolution compared to conventional techniques. Recent studies have demonstrated diffraction efficiencies as high as 21% an

improvement over conventional values of approximately 16% which was evidenced by enhanced fringe visibility and image clarity. Nevertheless, this still falls significantly short of the theoretical maximum diffraction efficiency of 100%.

Further research has explored the use of varying polarization states, such as right- and left-handed circular polarization, yielding diffraction efficiencies up to 60% and reconstructed light intensities of 110.38 μW . Similarly, linear polarization has achieved resolutions of up to 63%, with reconstructed intensities around 151.9 μW . While combining different polarization states has yielded marginal improvements, these studies maintained constant beam intensities, limiting potential enhancements.

To build upon these findings and expand the utility of polarization holography, the present study investigates the generation of circularly and elliptically polarized digital holograms by systematically varying the polarization states of both reference and object beams. The impact of these changes on hologram quality measured through parameters such as intensity, texture, and shape is carefully analyzed. Through advanced techniques like noise reduction and phase information retrieval, this work demonstrates the generation of high-resolution, high-clarity holograms. These findings underline the advantages of circular and elliptical polarization over linear methods and open new pathways for applications across diverse holographic systems.

Materials and Methods

When the object beam $E_O(x, y)$ and reference beam $E_R(x, y)$ interfere, they result to the recording of digital hologram whose equations are expressed using the following equations (Picart, 2015).

$$E_O(x, y) = a_o(x, y) \exp(-j\varphi_o(x, y)) \quad (1)$$

$$E_R(x, y) = a_r(x, y) \exp(-j\varphi_r(x, y)) \quad (2)$$

Where a_o and φ_o are the amplitude and phase distributions of the object beam respectively. a_R and φ_R are the amplitude and phase distributions of the reference beam respectively. The mixing of object and reference beam create an interference pattern with intensity given by $I_H(x, y)$ represented using the following equation in hologram plane;

$$I_H(x, y) = \{E_o(x, y) + E_R(x, y)\} \{E_o(x, y) + E_R(x, y)\}^* \quad (3)$$

$$I_H(x, y) = |E_o(x, y)|^2 + |E_R(x, y)|^2 + E_o(x, y) \{E_R(x, y)\}^* + \{E_o(x, y)\}^* E_R(x, y) \quad (4)$$

Where the first two terms in equation (4); $|E_o(x, y)|^2 + |E_R(x, y)|^2$ are constant terms of intensity while $E_o(x, y) \{E_R(x, y)\}^* + \{E_o(x, y)\}^* E_R(x, y)$ represent the complex amplitude of object beam and its complex conjugate. I_H is then recorded in the computer as intensity distribution which can then be reconstructed using several methods among them is convolution method, angular spectrum method, Fresnel method and others (Schnars & J ptner, 2002).

The holographic recording set-up is as shown by Figure 1. The Mach-Zehnder interferometer holographic experimental setup was used and the holograms were captured using a CCD camera with numerical reconstruction and propagation performed using convolution integral method (CIM). The recording was carried out in a darkroom with all sources of light having been blocked with minimized movements. A linearly polarized He-Ne laser of wavelength 632.8nm and power of 24mW was used as the source of coherent light. The beam spots were ensured that they were aligned in the same line with laser vertical height maintained at 11cm from the optical table. Microscope objective, pinhole, iris and collimating lens were used for the spatial filtering of the beam. The beam was later split into two beams; object beam (the beam from beam splitter that was made incident on Number 5 on ruler whose hologram was recorded) and reference beams (the beam

reflected from the beam splitter and made incident on CCD camera where the two beams interfered to form a hologram). To record the hologram, the two beams were superimposed on CCD camera and the holograms were observed on computer screen. The camera had the follows specifications; megapixels of 1440 X 1080 with pixel pitch of 3.45 μ m X 3.45 μ m and the object therefore, was supposed to be within the range of imaging area 4.968mm X 3.726mm. An optimum distance was achieved by getting a distance greater than the minimum distance obtained using the equation below;

$$d(d_o) = \frac{(d_o + N\Delta\xi)\Delta\xi}{\lambda} \quad (5)$$

Where d_o is the size of an object, N is the longer pixel size, $\Delta\xi$ is total pixel pitch, λ is the wavelength of the laser.

HWP 1 was used to vary the intensity of the s and p polarized beams which proceeded from the PBS while HWP 2 re-introduced the s and p polarized beams which were then used in the experiment while manipulating angle of polarization. To generate the circularly and elliptically polarized light, the linear polarizers and quarter wave plate (QWP) were used. These components were used to regulate the amount of light passing through by ensuring that maximum and minimum power were recorded. The linear polarizer 1 was placed in the path of the beam and it was rotated until the power reading in the power meter was maximum. The minimum power was recorded by subsequent optical components (QWP and LP2) that is; when the QWP was rotated at 70 $^\circ$, which was replicated by same minimum power reading in LP2. Therefore, this angle of 70 $^\circ$ was used as a point of reference in which the beam was rotated to produce varied polarization states to be used in recording of holograms. QWP has a property of producing right and left handed polarization depending on direction in which it is rotated. This property results to generation of polarization states which carry important information about the object recorded. Therefore, to achieve both right handed and left

handed circularly polarized light, the QWP was rotated by 45° on either sides from 70° while the recording the holograms. The process was repeated by rotating QWP by an angle of 50° from 70° to generate right handed and left handed elliptically polarized light. When the holograms were recorded, a lot of noise was

noticed from the screen and therefore to minimize this noise HWP 3 and another PBS were introduced in the path of the reference beam with the fast axis of HWP 3 kept at 90° with PBS only allowing p-polarized component to be used thus the hologram recorded as observed had minimal noise.

Figure 1. Digital Holograms Recording Set Up. M.O is Microscope Objective, C. Lens is Collimating Lens, HWP 1 is Half Wave Plate 1, PBS is Polarizing Beam Splitter, HWP 2 is Half Wave Plate 2, LP 1 is Linear Polarizer 1, QWP is Quarter-Wave Plate, LP 2 is Linear Polarizer 2, HWP 3 is Half Wave Plate 3, BS 2 is Beam Splitter 2, CCD is Charged-Coupled Device

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Results and Discussion

Digital holograms are inherently affected by noise due to their high sensitivity to the complex nature of light wave interference. In this study, noise reduction was achieved by subtracting background noise from the initial hologram specifically, by removing the fringes recorded without an object from the final hologram captured with the object present. This technique effectively isolates object-specific interference patterns and improves overall image quality.

Figure 2. The Reconstructed Images of Object when Noise has been Reduced (a) and (b); Circularly Polarized Holograms, 2(c) and 2(d); Elliptically Polarized Holograms

Noise reduction also serves as a useful approach for distinguishing the resolution differences between circularly and elliptically polarized holograms based on their visual characteristics. As shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), reconstructed holograms using circular polarization exhibited high clarity with well-defined features such as texture, shape, and depth. This improvement is attributed to reduced crosstalk within the holographic channel, resulting in enhanced image sharpness. Circular polarization further contributes to improved signal-to-noise ratio by filtering out unwanted light reflections, while its angle independence and superior depth perception contribute to the high resolution of the generated holograms.

In comparison, elliptically polarized holograms shown in Figures 2(c) and 2(d) revealed minor obscured regions in the reconstructed images. Nonetheless, their clarity was enhanced through improved depth encoding, which allows for more complex amplitude and phase representation. The extra degree of freedom in

elliptically polarized light facilitates encoding of additional information. Moreover, the suppression of unwanted reflections and the reduction of phase noise during reconstruction contributed to the overall improved quality of these holograms.

Figure 3(a) shows a hologram reconstructed at an angle of 25° , recorded using right-handed circularly polarized light. This hologram exhibits well-defined optical features, as the light interacts more effectively with the object. The reconstruction angle significantly influences the formation of interference fringes, which in turn affects the spatial frequency, Bragg selectivity, and reconstruction efficiency. Angles smaller than 25° lead to image degradation due to suboptimal fringe geometry. At this polarization state, the hologram is highly responsive to light, and reconstruction reveals a noticeable re-illumination effect. The high clarity and resolution can be attributed to the strong chiral optical response of the medium, which enables full transmission of right-handed circularly

polarized light while absorbing its left-handed counterpart.

Figure 3. The Reconstructed Images of Object Recorded when Varying the Polarization States of the Beam. (a) 25°, (b) 115°, (c) 20° and (d) 120°. (a) and (b) Circularly Polarized Holograms. (c) and (d) Elliptically Polarized Holograms

Figure 3(b) presents a hologram reconstructed at 115°, an angle that plays a crucial role in polarization-based image reconstruction. At this orientation, the light interacts with the medium to produce densely packed interference fringes that are highly sensitive to angular variations. The image remains clear due to the optimal Bragg matching conditions, where the geometry of the recorded fringes aligns precisely with the incident reconstruction beam. This alignment enhances both angular and spectral filtering, improving the fidelity of the reconstructed image.

Figures 3(c) and 3(d) depict holograms reconstructed using elliptically polarized light, with only a slight angular difference (5°) from the circularly polarized cases. Figure 3(c) corresponds to a hologram recorded with right-handed elliptically polarized light. This hologram also demonstrates enhanced contrast and a strong chiral response of the recording medium. The improved contrast results from finer and more uniformly spaced interference fringes. Since both interfering beams share the same ellipticity, fringe visibility is notably high. The vector nature of elliptically polarized light contributes to the encoding of complex amplitude and phase information within the hologram.

Figure 3(d) shows a hologram reconstructed at 120°, using left-handed elliptically polarized

light. The hologram is sensitive to polarization and encodes rich vector information, which enhances the detail and complexity of the reconstructed image. However, polarization mismatches during reconstruction may lead to some suppression of image features. Despite this, the hologram still exhibits high resolution due to the matching playback polarization, angle sensitivity, and strong illumination. The high amplitude of the interfering beams also contributes to the observed image sharpness and overall quality.

Figure 4(a) displays the phase information retrieved from a right-handed circularly polarized hologram reconstructed at an angle of 25°. The phase distribution spans a broad range along the x-axis from approximately 3.0 mm to 0.5 mm with a vertical projection peak occurring at 0.6 mm. This wide phase range indicates strong light–object interaction, enabling clear distinction of all object features. At this optimal reconstruction angle, the spatial characteristics of the object such as depth and shape are effectively resolved. The hologram captures both phase and amplitude properties, and due to well-defined fringe spacing and fine structural details, the phase information retrieved is rich and accurate. Additionally, portions of the object that were partially illuminated by light appear in the range 3.5 mm to 3.0 mm, represented by the blue regions in the phase map.

Figure 4. The Phase Reconstructed Values of Object Recorded at Circularly Polarized State. (a) 25° and (b) 115°

In contrast, Figure 4(b) shows a reduction in the intensity and range of retrieved phase information. The phase span narrows to 2.2 mm to 0.5 mm along the x-axis, with a vertical coordinate (y-axis) projection peak at 0.4 mm. This indicates a steeper phase gradient, likely resulting from a larger optical path difference. While the resolution remains high, the reduced phase range is attributed to tightly packed interference fringes, which demand precise matching of recording and reconstruction

angles. At this angle, polarization sensitivity becomes critical; even slight deviations can introduce polarization distortions, potentially limiting the utility of such holograms in high-precision applications. Additionally, alterations in the s- and p-polarized light components during reconstruction may contribute to reduced phase accuracy, as changes in polarization state can affect both phase retrieval and overall hologram fidelity.

Figure 5. The Phase Reconstructed Values of Images Reconstructed at Elliptically Polarized State. (a) 20° and (b) 120°

Figure 5(a) presents the phase reconstruction of a right-handed elliptically polarized hologram. The retrieved phase information is limited, ranging from 1.6 mm to 0.5 mm along the x-axis. This range is significantly narrower compared to the phase distributions observed in circularly polarized holograms. Within this interval, faint red and blue regions are visible, indicating minimal interaction between the polarized light and the object. This limited interaction is likely due to partial light obstruction by optical components in the setup—namely LP1, QWP, and LP2—which reduced the intensity of the beam reaching the object. Additionally, unequal optical paths taken by different portions of the wavefront introduced spatial phase shifts and phase gradients, further limiting the reconstructed phase detail. Nevertheless, some degree of phase information was successfully encoded into the hologram, albeit at a reduced level.

Figure 5(b) shows the phase distribution for a hologram recorded with left-handed circularly polarized light. In this case, there is significantly stronger interaction between the light and the object, as evidenced by the deep red coloration reaching up to 1.5 mm intensity within the 3.0 mm to 0.5 mm spatial range along the x-axis. The absence of blue tones in this reconstruction suggests that the entire object surface was illuminated and recorded, with no significant portions left out. This indicates a comprehensive phase capture, resulting from strong optical coupling between the beam and the object. Notably, the data suggests that as the polarization angle increases, the quantity and quality of reconstructed phase information also improves in circular polarization.

Overall, a comparison of phase values from both circularly and elliptically polarized holograms demonstrates that phase information was well captured and reconstructed, showing clear improvement over linearly polarized holograms, which were previously limited in their phase encoding capability.

Conclusion

In this study, digital holograms were experimentally generated using various polarization states to investigate their impact on hologram quality. Circularly and elliptically polarized light embody crucial polarization characteristics that significantly influence the reconstruction process. The reconstructed holograms demonstrated high clarity, highlighting the critical role of beam polarization in enhancing the quality of digital holography.

We successfully produced circularly and elliptically polarized digital holograms featuring distinct attributes such as surface texture, depth, and shape features that linear holograms fail to capture with the same precision. The analysis included detailed examination of depth information, interference fringe patterns, and hologram contrast, complemented by phase reconstruction and noise reduction techniques for accurate hologram evaluation.

Overall, circularly polarized holograms consistently exhibited superior resolution compared to their elliptically polarized counterparts, underscoring their potential advantage in applications demanding high-fidelity holographic imaging.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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